

IMPACTS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON BRAZILIAN E-COMMERCE LOGISTICS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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Abstract: With the advent of the Covid-19 Pandemic, which spread rapidly from March 2020 across Brazil, a decline in face-to-face commerce was observed and the need to adapt the tools used in negotiations for service by electronic means. In view of this scenario, investments were made in technologies to optimize processes associated with e-commerce, as an example of the use of artificial intelligence in the logistics of this type of commerce. From this perspective, this article aimed to identify the impacts of artificial intelligence on Brazilian e-commerce logistics during the Covid-19 pandemic. The methodological process consisted of carrying out a descriptive qualitative research based on the development of a bibliographic survey. Based on the research carried out, an increase in e-commerce revenue was observed during the COVID-19 disaster state period (2020 - 2021), in addition to the adoption of technological tools associated with artificial intelligence in the logistical process of the e-commerce. Given the above, it was concluded that the implementation of artificial intelligence in the e-commerce logistics process promotes a positive impact, since it adds value to the products and services offered, inserts the company in the competitive market and promotes the improvement of the efficiency of the process.

Keywords: *E-commerce. Logistics. Artificial intelligence.*

INTRODUCTION

With the exponential increase in the world population, there is also a growth in the demand for goods and services. Based on the increase in this demand, the market has been

seeking the insertion of new tools to improve customer service and reach a greater number of customers, one of which is the adoption of e-commerce.

- *commerce* or electronic commerce aims at the connection between customer and company through electronic means, aiming to promote the sale of products and services, creating a direct relationship between demand and supply. The strategy had its implementation milestone in the 90s, when Amazon and other companies started to adopt it. In Brazil, electronic commerce was disseminated from the initiative of Booknet, a bookstore purchased by Submarino in 1999 and a pioneer of *e-commerce* in the country, with the commerce strategy later adopted by other companies (BERMAN, 2022).

At the same time that *e-commerce* was expanding, artificial intelligence (AI) was also developing. AI has enabled the automation of the decision-making process in a series of situations that are considered complex, performing tasks that, until then, were related to human intelligence (DONEDA *et al.* , 2018).

It is important to identify the impacts of artificial intelligence on e-commerce logistics, as technologies become more comprehensive every day and AI is being seen as an important tool in the logistics process. Thus, it is questioned about the impacts generated by the insertion of artificial intelligence in the logistics of Brazilian *e-commerce* during the Covid-19 Pandemic, which started in March 2020, the state of calamity being recognized through Legislative Decree n° 06/ 2020, and had its confrontation decrees revoked in May 2022, through Decree n° 11.077/2022.

Given the above, this work has the general objective of identifying the impacts of artificial intelligence on Brazilian e-commerce logistics during the Covid-19 Pandemic, with the following specific objectives: (1) analyzing the behavior of *e-commerce* during the pandemic; (2) collect information and data on the use of artificial intelligence in e-commerce logistics; and (3) to analyze the impacts of the adoption of artificial intelligence in the logistic process of *e-commerce* .

METHODOLOGY

The development of this work was based on three stages: (1) analysis of *e-commerce* during the pandemic; (2) gathering information and data on the use of artificial intelligence in e-commerce logistics; and (3) identification of the impacts of the adoption of artificial intelligence in the logistic process of e-commerce.

The first two stages were proceeded from the accomplishment of bibliographical research. This type of research can be defined as gathering information extracted mainly from

books and scientific articles, which in turn will be treated according to the reference objective (GIL, 2002).

The research was promoted through the Google Scholar online data platform (<https://scholar.google.com.br/?hl=pt>), using the following keywords: “ *e-commerce* ”, “electronic commerce”, “logistics of *e-commerce* ” and “artificial intelligence in logistics”.

For the present study, a descriptive line of research with a qualitative character was adopted. As for the concept of descriptive research, it can be said that “research of this type has as its primary objective the description of the characteristics of a given population or phenomenon or the establishment of relationships between variables” (GIL, 2008).

Initially, a survey was carried out on the history of the use of artificial intelligence in the logistics area, and then the use of this tool in electronic commerce was covered. For this purpose, academic articles and other scientific research on the use of AI in the e-commerce logistics process were considered.

From the bibliographic survey carried out and the analyzes carried out, the impacts of artificial intelligence in the logistical process of Brazilian electronic commerce were highlighted.

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND E-COMMERCE LOGISTICS

The advent of the internet takes place in the mid-60s and 70s and had as its forerunner Joseph Licklider, a computer scientist, who discussed the concept of "Galactic Network", where the interconnection between computers on a worldwide scale was thought, enabling the access for all to a kind of electronic library (CALAZANS and LIMA, 2013). Over the years, this form of communication has been perfected and adapted to new technologies and emerging needs.

Technologies are in increasing expansion, reaching different sectors and spaces over the years. An example of this expansion is the insertion of technologies in commercial negotiations, as in electronic commerce. Electronic commerce or *e-commerce* is conceptualized as a method of acquiring products, services and information through the internet, being marked by the use of digital tools to carry out the operations that will be carried out (VISSOTTO and BONIATI, 2013).

While *e-commerce* spread around the world, artificial intelligence, which began in 1956, was also in full development. Artificial intelligence is associated with the use of systems or machines that aim to approach human intelligence to perform tasks based on interactive commands and data collection. AI has enabled the automation of the decision-making process

in a series of situations that are considered complex, performing tasks that, until then, were related to human intelligence (DONEDA *et al.* , 2018).

AI has been positively adding to the entire process involving logistics, becoming increasingly essential for building a more efficient process. According to Wilson (2005, apud NOVAES, 2007), logistics is defined as the process of planning, implementing and controlling services and associated information, the flow and storage of products efficiently, with the aim of meeting the requirements of the consumer, thus meeting the demands from the point of origin to the point of consumption.

The association of artificial intelligence to *e-commerce* favors internal transactions and logistical processes, benefiting the growth of companies in the market. According to Jack London, the creator of Booknet, it is necessary to keep up with the technological advances in e-commerce and one should never stop in time, bearing in mind that today's *e-commerce* is not the same as that of the past, much less of the future. (WAKAI, 2016).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Electronic trading has become extremely widespread and competitive, because, with technological advances and the growing number of customers, the insertion of new tools that can contribute to the intrinsic processes of the consumer goods industry has become essential.

Artificial intelligence plays a fundamental role in the continuous technological advancement in *e-commerce logistics*, as it is through the insertion of AI in logistical processes that it is possible to obtain more efficiency in the activities carried out, as an example of optimizing the delivery of products.

During the pandemic period, there was an increase in *e-commerce*, in the period from 2020 to 2022, with regard to the turnover of sales made, as can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1- Evolution of *e-commerce* in Brazil

Source : Adapted from NielsenIQ Ebit (2022)

Based on Figure 1, the data presented had as reference the period of the first half of each year, with data from the years 2020, 2021 and 2022 being arranged. of 2020 presented a turnover of BRL 76.2 billion, with the value in 2021 of BRL 111.8 billion. Comparing the two years mentioned above, it appears that there was a 47% (forty-seven percent) increase in *e-commerce revenues* in Brazil.

Analyzing the period 2021 *versus* 2022, where the first half of 2021 had revenues of R\$ 111.8 billion and 2022 of R\$ 118.6 billion, it can be seen that there has been an evolution, but in a milder way previously observed period (2020/2021), now being the increment of 6% (six percent).

- *commerce* is the modality of commerce consolidated as one of the most efficient and effective of all times and, in this way, it is increasingly revolutionizing the logistics area of companies.

During the pandemic, the logistics sector was deeply affected, since one of the processes carried out in the logistics activity is associated with face-to-face contact with the end customer, which is carried out through people specialized in deliveries. However, with the advance of Covid-19 cases, several measures were being implemented by governments in their three spheres: federal, state and municipal.

Among the measures adopted, we mention the restriction of face-to-face contact, resulting from the adoption of social isolation, which in some cases occurred partially and, in others, completely, as in the “curfew” period. The coping measures associated with the

aforementioned episode are listed in Law nº 13.979/2020, which follows an excerpt associated with its Art. 3rd:

Art. 3 To face the public health emergency of international importance dealt with in this Law, the authorities may adopt, within the scope of their competences, the following measures, among others: I - isolation; II - quarantine; III - determination of compulsory performance of: a) medical examinations; b) laboratory tests; c) collection of clinical samples; d) vaccination and other prophylactic measures; or e) specific medical treatments; III-A – mandatory use of personal protective masks; IV - epidemiological study or investigation; V - exhumation, necropsy, cremation and handling of the corpse; VI – exceptional and temporary restriction, by highways, ports or airports, of: a) entering and leaving the country; and b) interstate and intercity transportation (BRASIL, 2020).

As a result of the Covid-19 pandemic, some actions were adopted by companies in order to avoid possible damage to their employees, such as isolation and quarantine. It is noteworthy that these mechanisms reflected directly on logistics, as the face-to-face business model was affected by the reduction in population circulation (SEBRAE, 2022).

As the restrictions imposed, which had a direct impact on logistics activities, companies needed to reinvent themselves, that is, seek new process models to optimize their activities, thus ensuring the performance of the services provided, where the great ally for such a problem was the artificial intelligence (AI) technology.

Companies apply the use of AI in order to redesign the structure for carrying out tasks and thus promote improvements in their skills and, in this way, allow mechanization to no longer be used, adding value to products and services, bringing the end customer closer each more and more to their environment, enabling new experiences for them (ORACLE, 2022).

Given the need for companies to reinvent themselves in the logistics area and, consequently, the search for ways to add value to their chain and increase their revenues, several alternatives began to be considered, among which we can mention the use of deliveries carried out autonomously.

Autonomous deliveries are associated with the creation and use of robots (physical and virtual) and/or drones with dimensions appropriate to the type of activity that is aimed at, these mechanisms being controlled by artificial intelligence. This model brings in its essence the duty to satisfy customer expectations from the initial service, with the receipt of the order, to the final stage, where the requested product or service is delivered.

The use of robots is already considered fundamental in the internal logistics process of

some companies, with robotics enabling greater product turnover and agility in deliveries (CORDENONSI, 2022).

Companies make high-cost technological investments, but obtain economic returns by reaching new consumers, in addition to adding efficiency in deliveries and even low costs with human labor.

CONSIDERATIONS FINALS

It was found that during the pandemic there was a growth in *e-commerce revenues* in Brazil. This increase may be related to the need to adapt to the measures adopted during the state of calamity, due to the advance of the COVID-19 pandemic in the country, at which time social isolation and quarantine were implemented, reflecting on the reduction in the circulation of the virus. population and, consequently, in the decline of face-to-face sales.

As a result of the increase in *e-commerce demands*, it was necessary to adapt the mechanisms used in the companies' sales processes, promoting strategies to optimize logistical processes. An example of the improvement promoted was the implementation of the use of robots and drones, used for autonomous deliveries. It is noteworthy that the implementation of this technology is made possible by artificial intelligence, which enables the command of these tools.

It was found that the adoption of artificial intelligence in the logistics process promotes a positive impact, as it adds value to the products and services offered and inserts the company in the competitive market. By adding state-of-the-art technology, the use of AI enables economic growth and, through new applications and software development, also promotes a gradual reduction in the organization's effective costs, and can be considered as an investment by organizations.

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